

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA ON 2-SUBSTITUTED PHENYL-4-(4'-NN-Bis- β -CARBOXYETHYLAMINO-BENZYLIDENE)-5-OXAZOLONES(I)

Sl. No.	R	Colour	Colour of the spots	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Mol. Formula	%N	
							Found	Calcd.
1.	H	Orange	Orange	226	67.2	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₂	6.81	6.86
2.	Cl(o-)	Bright yellow	Yellow	231	40.9	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₂ Cl	6.41	6.33
3.	Cl(p-)	Yellow	Yellow	234	47.7	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₂ Cl	6.39	6.33
4.	NO ₂ (o-)	Orange yellow	Orange yellow	248	35.5	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₃	9.71	9.29
5.	NO ₂ (p-)	Deep yellow	Deep yellow	256	48.8	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₃	9.79	9.29
6.	Cl(2)NO ₂ (5)	Yellow	Yellow	238	33.2	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₂ Cl	8.41	8.62
7.	Cinnamoyl	Red	Red	240	44.5	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₂	6.84	6.45

effective in producing different colours from yellow to red with acyl glycines on paper.

The colours of the spots have been given in the Table I.

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Studies on Biologically Active Agents : Synthesis of Variously Substituted N¹-(4-substituted phenoxy acetyl/benzoyl secondary amines)-N²-Substituted Aryl Thioureas as Possible CNS, Anticonvulsant and MAO Inhibitory Agents

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SUBSTITUTED thioureas are known to possess pharmacodynamic properties¹⁻⁴. The present communication describes the synthesis of thiourea derivatives by incorporating heterocyclic moiety in

the hope that resulting product may have higher biological activities.

These substituted thioureas have been prepared by the condensation of *p*-nitro phenoxy and *p*-nitro-benzoyl chloride with secondary amine. Nitro group was reduced and then reacted with aryl isothiocyanate to obtain the desired product. Some of them were screened, which showed encouraging results.

Experimental

Synthesis of p-nitrophenoxy acetyl/benzoyl secondary amines :

They were prepared according to the method of Baker *et al*⁵. Melting points of *p*-nitro phenoxy acetyl and benzoyl dicyclohexylamine were found to be 302° and 200° respectively.

Synthesis of p-amino phenoxy acetyl/benzoyl secondary amines :

They were prepared by the method of Richard and Furst⁶. They are shown in Table 1.

Synthesis of N¹-(4-substituted phenoxy acetyl/benzoyl amines)-N²-substituted aryl thioureas :

They were prepared according to the method reported by George *et al*⁷. Arylisothiocyanate (0.01 mole) was added to a solution of *p*-amino-phenoxyacetyl or *p*-aminobenzoyl secondary amine (0.01 mole) in ethyl alcohol (25 ml). The mixture was heated under reflux for 4 hours. A solid mass was obtained, which was filtered and crystallized from suitable solvents. They are given in Table 1.

Elemental analyses of C, N and H were found within $\pm 0.5\%$ of theoretical and calculated values.

Pharmacological studies :

Toxicity studies : Acute toxicity study was performed with substituted thioureas. These compounds were administered intraperitoneally in albino mice and their approximate LD₅₀ were determined by conventional procedure⁸.

NOTES

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	LD ₅₀ *	Anticonvulsant activity Protection %	Mortality %	Monoamine oxidase inhibition %
$Z = \text{Pyrrolidino}, X = \text{OCH}_2\text{C}(=\text{O})-$							
1.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}-\text{C}(=\text{O})-$	105	75	681	40	40	40
2.	$p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}-\text{C}(=\text{O})-$	190	63	681	40	60	70
3.	$o\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}-\text{C}(=\text{O})-$	165	65	—	—	—	—
4.	$p\text{-OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}-\text{C}(=\text{O})-$	200	54	—	—	—	—
5.	$p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4$	185	61	825	40	60	67
6.	$\alpha\text{-C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NHC}(=\text{O})-$	175	56	—	—	—	—
7.	H	90	38	—	—	—	—
$Z = \text{Morpholino}, X = -\text{OCH}_2\text{C}(=\text{O})-$							
8.	$p\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NHC}(=\text{O})-$	165	67	—	—	—	—
9.	$p\text{-BrC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}-\text{C}(=\text{O})-$	105	57	—	—	—	—
10.	$p\text{-C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NH}-\text{C}(=\text{O})-$	170	59	—	—	—	—
11.	H	79	48	—	—	—	—
$Z = \text{Piperidino}, X = -\text{OCH}_2\text{C}(=\text{O})-$							
12.	$p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{NHC}(=\text{S})-$	151	61	1000	20	80	—
13.	$p\text{-OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{NHC}(=\text{S})-$	130	55	—	—	—	—
14.	$p\text{-BrC}_6\text{H}_4-\text{NH}-\text{C}(=\text{S})-$	160	55	>1000	60	20	—
15.	$\alpha\text{-C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NH}-\text{C}(=\text{S})-$	115	60	—	—	—	—
16.	H	70	50	—	—	—	—
$Z = \text{Dicyclohexylamino}, X = -\text{OCH}_2-\text{C}(=\text{O})-$							
17.	$p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{NHC}(=\text{S})-$	202	67	—	—	—	—
18.	$p\text{-ClCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{NHC}(=\text{S})-$	147-48	40	825	60	40	—
19.	$p\text{-BrC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NHC}(=\text{S})-$	120	58	—	—	—	—
20.	$\alpha\text{-C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NHC}(=\text{S})-$	123	33	—	—	—	—
21.	H	240	48	—	—	—	—

(Table 1 Contd.)

Sr. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	LD ₅₀ *	Anticonvulsant activity Protection%	Anticonvulsant activity Mortality%	Monoamine oxidase inhibition%
$Z = \text{Piperidino}, X = \begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \\ -\text{C}- \end{array}$							
22.	$p\text{-OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}-\begin{array}{c} \text{S} \\ \\ -\text{C}- \end{array}$	180	53	-4	—	—	—
23.	$p\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}-\begin{array}{c} \text{S} \\ \\ -\text{C}- \end{array}$	190	50	1000	60	20	62
24.	$p\text{-BrC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}-\begin{array}{c} \text{S} \\ \\ -\text{C}- \end{array}$	200	48	681	60	40	—
25.	$\alpha\text{-C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NH}-\begin{array}{c} \text{S} \\ \\ -\text{C}- \end{array}$	185	57	825	20	60	—
26.	H	160	38	—	—	—	—
$Z = \text{Dicyclohexylamino}, X = \begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \\ -\text{C}- \end{array}$							
27.	$p\text{-OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}-\begin{array}{c} \text{S} \\ \\ -\text{C}- \end{array}$	215	50	—	—	—	—
28.	$p\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}-\begin{array}{c} \text{S} \\ \\ -\text{C}- \end{array}$	234	64	—	—	—	—
29.	$p\text{-BrC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}-\begin{array}{c} \text{S} \\ \\ -\text{C}- \end{array}$	205	47	825	20	80	—
30.	$\alpha\text{-C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NH}-\begin{array}{c} \text{S} \\ \\ -\text{C}- \end{array}$	245	48	—	—	—	49
31.	H	242	48	—	—	—	—

In-vivo effect on Gross behaviour : It was determined⁹ on simple reflexes and behaviour after intraperitoneal administration in albino mice.

Anticonvulsant activity : It was studied¹⁰ against pentylenetetrazole induced seizures on mice.

Monoamine Oxidase activity : Spectrophotometric method¹¹ was applied for the determination of monoamine oxidase activity of rat brain homogenate using benzylamine as substrate.

Results and Discussion

The approximate LD₅₀ value of these compounds ranged from 681 to 1000 mg/kg indicating their low toxicity associated with the compounds and all the compounds of this series had CNS stimulant action.

Anticonvulsant activity was reflected from 20-80%. The presence of *p*-chlorophenyl ring at R position of N² and oxymethyl carbonyl at position X exhibited maximum (80%) activity, while methyl and unsubstituted phenyl group at the same position showed low activity (20%). Protection value further diminished from *ortho* to *para* position, due to

presence of electron donating group and activity gradually increases due to presence of electron attracting group at the same position.

Monoamine oxidase activity of these compounds was found to be just reverse. The presence of

$-\text{OCH}_2-\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ || \\ -\text{C}- \end{array}$ group at X exhibited greater degree of activity and >C=O group reduced the activity at the same position.

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On the Dicumyl Peroxide Vulcanisation of Rubber

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DICUMYL peroxide (DCP) vulcanisation of rubbers has attracted wide interest in recent years because of its simple chemistry and quantitative results where one carbon to carbon crosslink is formed per molecule of peroxide decomposed¹. The sulfur vulcanisation of natural rubber (NR) is known to be characterised by a reversion in crosslinking, just after reaching the optimum cure time, and it also produces vulcanisate with poor aging properties.

The addition of DCP in sulfur curing system checks both these defects through the inclusion of Carbon-Carbon crosslinks. However, the accelerators, present in the system, may affect adversely² on the DCP-NR curing system. In the present paper, the nature and the extent of the effect of the commonly used accelerators on the DCP-NR vulcanisation system has been investigated. The accelerators used are 2-mercaptobenzothiazole (MBT), diphenyl guanidine (DPG) and tetramethyl thiuram disulfide (TMTD).

Experimental

The following sets of compounding formulations were studied. All the formulations given below are in Phr (Parts per hundred of rubber).

NR 100	NR 100	NR 100
DCP 1.0	DCP 1.0	DCP 1.0
MBT, DPG	MBT 1.0	MBT 1.0
or TMTD 0.0,	DPG 0.0, 0.5,	TMTD 0.0, 0.5,
0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0	1.0	1.0

Mixing was done on a laboratory size two roll mill at 50° to a constant Mooney viscosity. Each stock was cured in an electrically heated press at 140° ± 1° and a pressure of 281 psi for various times. Crosslink density of each vulcanisate was determined by equilibrium swelling in benzene as described in the earlier publication³ of this laboratory.

Results and Discussion

Vulcanisation of natural rubber by dicumyl peroxide has been studied by several workers and the crosslinking reaction has been established beyond doubt to follow a free radical mechanism which can be summarised as follows :

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